

Ultra-Fast Chemical Analysis With Raman

With uCAIR, we strive to develop a novel laser technology combined with AI-enhanced signal processing, creating a pioneering Raman-based diagnostic system suitable for endoscopic procedures in oncology and beyond. By detecting molecular-level disruptions in the life cycle of biological cells, our real-time and non-invasive imaging solution holds the potential to significantly improve healthcare.

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uCAIR

UCAIR TARGETS

Showcasing Better Future Diagnosis

By the end of the project, we will provide a prototype of the uCAIR platform. This prototype will deliver increased specificity and sensitivity in diagnosis in disease from biological tissue and body liquid samples.

We will demonstrate the uCAIR technologies in two realistic use cases involving the characterisation of biopsy tissues and urine samples from bladder cancer patients.

Drs. Ning Liu and Christophe Silien in the Labs of the Bernal Institute, University of Limerick

Biopsy-Tissue

CASE STUDY

During the first case study we will examine biopsy tissues from cancer patients with the uCAIR system. We will compare the chemometric diagnosis specificity and sensitivity with both state-of-the-art spectroscopy complementary technologies: Fourier-Transform-Infrared-Spectroscopy (FTIR) and Raman in real-time imaging.

Microfluidics

CASE STUDY

Biomarkers are measurable parameters of biological processes that have prognostic or diagnostic significance. In the second case study we will investigate molecular biomarkers from urine using a specially designed microfluidic system in combination with uCAIR. We intend to reach a 90% specificity in real-time.

Earlier diagnosis such as biofluid-based screening of bladder cancer can lead to better prognosis for patients.

Technology Roadmap

uCAIR will pave the way for a technology roadmap for in vivo optical biopsy and endomicroscopy for clinical purposes. The design of uCAIR will facilitate translation of the novel ultra-fast Raman technology's application spectrum, extending its reach beyond the medical domain.

The consortium technology roadmap targets rapid societal impact in the medical instrument market and also ambitious scientific and economic impacts with a faster pace of discoveries in materials and pharmaceuticals.

ABOUT uCAIR

Breakthrough Photonic Technology for Early Diagnosis of Cancer

Breakthrough photonic technologies are needed to perform rapid and standardised ex vivo, in vivo or in vitro diagnosis – diagnosis performed either on living tissue outside or within the human body or on any material in a test tube – at high speed and sensitivity.

This can be achieved by employing extended spectral analysis for an accurate reflection of cellular life cycles and diseases processes, thereby enhancing specificity. Within uCAIR, we will develop this breakthrough technology.

Next-level Raman Spectroscopy: Increased Quality and Speed of Diagnosis from Human Tissue

We will set up a coherent Raman microspectroscopy platform to enable increased quality and speed of diagnosis from human tissue, for instance during procedures of endomicroscopy. Endomicroscopy makes it possible to obtain microscopic images of the examined area as part of conventional endoscopy.

Our goal is to achieve ultra-fast coherent Raman scattering through the development of an advanced laser technology covering a broad spectral and temporal range.

uCAIR Technological Innovations

- Design and fabrication of an innovative versatile laser source for hyperspectral imaging with near-infrared picosecond (NIR) excitation.
- Design and fabrication of innovative Photonics Crystal Fibres (PCF) and Nanofibers (NF).
- High fidelity, short dwell time λ -scan photodetection and digitisation.
- AI-enhanced data qualification system.

AT A GLANCE

THE uCAIR PLATFORM

Workflow of the uCAIR Photonics Platform

The uCAIR innovation: Novel photonics and AI-enhanced process will improve the Raman measurements. The real-time hyperspectral imaging will be fiber-ready for further development in endomicroscopy.

About Raman Spectroscopy – An Ideal Tool for Biophotonics

Named after the Indian physicist C.V. Raman, Raman spectroscopy is a technique used to analyse the vibrational modes of molecules by measuring the scattered light resulting from interactions with a laser beam. It is often used to investigate material properties, for example of pigments in art objects.

Ultra-fast coherent Raman scattering refers to a variant of Raman spectroscopy that utilises ultra-short laser pulses to induce coherent vibrational excitations in molecules, enabling rapid and sensitive chemical imaging with high spatial resolution.

The combination of chemical specificity, non-destructive analysis, label-free detection, real-time capabilities, and microscopic resolution, makes coherent Raman microspectroscopy an exceptionally practical and powerful tool for biophotonics research and biomedical applications.

Artificial Intelligence as Enhancer

We will integrate an AI expert system to speed up signal recording without reducing overall accuracy for automatic classification of molecular Raman signatures.

Our AI expert system will undergo a rigorous training using robust datasets derived from series of measurements conducted on specimens with progressively increasing complexity. A quality metric will be developed measuring the fit between uCAIR recordings and expected Raman signatures.

We intend to also use the AI to control the laser and microscope to speed up the analysis, by contrast to current approaches where the AI is solely used to process data that is acquired in a standard way.

Drs. Sebnem Garip Ustaoglu and Ayca Dogan in the Labs of the Altinbas University

About bladder cancer

Bladder cancers are the fifth most common cancer in Europe, with about 67,000 deaths and 204,000 new diagnoses in 2020*. Due to its aggressiveness and complexities in stage identification, the need for accurate and rapid diagnostic procedures is proportionally high. A better ex vivo analysis of tissue biopsies as well as live detection in vivo during cystoscopy would be possible with the more precise urological surgical technique.

*European Cancer Patient Coalition. Bladder Cancer Awareness Month Campaign. <https://ecpc.org/get-involved/bladder-cancer-awarenessmonth-campaign/>. IARC. Online analysis table. <https://gco.iarc.fr/today/online-analysis-table?v=2020&mode=cancer&mode=can> Accessed October 2022.

Consortium

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“We want to break through the technological barriers that currently prevent widescale adoption of Raman in clinical practices. To this end, the consortium is uniquely placed to achieve this goal as the project brings together world-recognised experts covering the whole development chain including R&D photonics SMEs, research laboratories in optics and cell biology, and world-leading microscopists and clinicians to create an innovative, versatile, practical multimodal photonics platform that will enhance and speed up the way cells are examined by scientists and healthcare professionals.”

Stakeholder Mailinglist

UCAIR has set up a mailing list for interested stakeholders. If you wish to subscribe please contact us via email ucair-stakeholder@vdivde-it.de indicating your stakeholder group among the following: R&D and Academic researchers | Pharmaceutical R&D stakeholders | Chemometric-based diagnosis microscopy research community | AI/ML development community | Photonic health stakeholders | Endoscopy stakeholders | Patients | General public

Facts

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42 months

Funding: EUR 5 Mio.

Coordinator: University of Limerick Consortium of 11 partners from 6 countries | 5 SMEs

